

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B412
 Date: 31 Oct 2008
 Take Off: 09:47:21
 Landing: 14:52:43
 Flight Time 5h 05m 22s

Campaign: VOCALS

Operating Area: South east pacific ocean off coast of northern Chile

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Tracy Hill	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Phil Brown	Met Office	
5	Mission Scientist 2	Keith Bower	Manchester University	
6	Mission Scientist 3	Paul Barrett	Met Office	
7	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM	
8	Core Chem / AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
9	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
10	SWS/SHIMS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	
11	CCN	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	
12	Core Chem training	Guy Gratton	FAAM	
13	ARIES/MARSS	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
14	AMS/SP2	Paul Williams	Manchester University	
15	Wet Neph / PSAP / Filters	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office	
16	VACC	Mark Bart	Leeds University	
17	Manchester cloud	Jonny Crosier	Manchester University	
18	CVI	James Bowles	Met Office	

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B412
 Date: 31 October 2008
 Project: VOCALS
 Location: Pacific off northern coast of Chile

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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091729		gin	0.00 kft	023	started
094211		ASP	0.08 kft	020	open
094721		T/O	0.04 kft	199	Arica
094817	095457	Profile 1	0.86 - 6.0 kft	199	start at t/o
094827		heimann	1.1 kft	229	open
095005		JW	2.0 kft	227	on
095457	100103	transit	6.0 kft	224	
100104	100727	Profile 2	6.0 - -.04 kft	225	50ft
100421		cloud	2.6 kft	223	top 2800
100514		cloud	1.7 kft	229	bottom 1800
100727	100834	Profile 3	-.04 - 0.40 kft	224	50ft 500ft above surface
100834	101837	Run 1.1	0.40 - 0.39 kft	226	500ft above surface
101837	101935	Profile 4	0.39 - 1.2 kft	221	
101935	102936	Run 1.2	1.2 kft	227	
102746		nev	1.2 kft	267	zero 1300ft - 500ft below cloud
102803		JW	1.2 kft	267	zero
102922		r 1.2	1.3 kft	267	1300ft 500ft below cloud 1019
102936	103044	Profile 5	1.2 - 2.3 kft	268	
103044	104040	Run 1.3	2.3 - 2.5 kft	270	
103146		r 1.3	2.4 kft	267	in cloud, broken layer
104040	104232	Profile 6	2.5 - 4.3 kft	268	
104232	104759	Profile 7	4.3 - -.08 kft	266	50ft
104759	104847	Profile 8	-.08 - 0.34 kft	268	50ft
104848	105850	Run 2.1	0.36 - 0.34 kft	270	
105012		r 2.1	0.37 kft	268	500ft
105733		heimann	0.34 kft	272	cal 09
105851	110015	Profile 9	0.34 - 1.7 kft	269	
110016	111021	Run 2.2	1.7 kft	268	
110117		JW	1.7 kft	265	zero
110127		nev	1.6 kft	266	zero
111021	111154	Profile 10	1.7 - 3.2 kft	269	
111154	112216	Run 2.3	3.2 kft	274	
111214		r 2.3	3.2 kft	273	in cloud
112217	112300	Profile 11	3.2 - 3.5 kft	268	
112301	113357	Run 2.4	3.5 - 3.6 kft	271	
113357	113549	Profile 12	3.6 - 5.4 kft	269	
113549	114231	Profile 13	5.4 - -.12 kft	269	50 ft
113614		reversal	5.1 kft	269	5500ft
113713		cloud	4.0 kft	267	top 4500
113919		cloud	1.8 kft	264	base ?? indistinct
114231	114319	Profile 14	-.12 - 0.32 kft	266	50 ft 500 ft
114319	115331	Run 3.1	0.32 kft	264	500 ft
115331	115535	Profile 15	0.32 - 2.1 kft	269	
115535	120534	Run 3.2	2.1 kft	272	
115621		r 3.2	2.1 kft	269	2300ft
115653		JW	2.1 kft	268	zero
115711		nev	2.1 kft	270	zero
115753		r 3.2	2.1 kft	267	below cloud base
120535	120728	Profile 16	2.1 - 3.9 kft	271	
120728	120802	Run 3.3	3.9 kft	272	in cloud run
120859	121740	r 3.3	3.9 kft	264	end as start profile
121740	121940	Profile 17	3.8 - 5.7 kft	187	above cloud intercomparison
122058	123101	Run 4.1	5.6 kft	089	
123102	123244	Profile 18	5.6 - 4.4 kft	090	
123245	124259	Run 4.2	4.4 kft	095	
123323		heimann	4.4 kft	096	cal 06
123613		heimann	4.4 kft	097	cal 07
124034		heimann	4.4 kft	092	cal 08
124300	124637	Profile 19	4.4 - 0.29 kft	094	

124637	125812	Run 4.3	0.29 - 0.33 kft	092
124803		!	0.28 kft	092 c130 run start position
125812	131037	climb to fl230	0.33 - 23.0 kft	093
131037	141841	Run 5	23.0 kft	273
131410		r5	23.0 kft	094 heading eastwards
131504		Sonde 1	23.0 kft	098 78W
132453		Sonde 2	23.0 kft	090 77W
133455		Sonde 3	23.0 kft	089 76W
134505		Sonde 4	23.0 kft	086 75W
135516		Sonde 5	23.0 kft	088 74W
140536		Sonde 6	23.0 kft	088 73W
141620		Sonde 7	23.0 kft	086 72W
141841	145242	Profile 20	23.0 - 0.05 kft	035 Arica
144118		p20	4.9 kft	052 int @ 5000ft
144453		p20	4.8 kft	023 resumed
145243		Land	0.05 kft	201 Arica
145400		asp	0.06 kft	137 closed

B412 Track 31-OCT-08

SCAR -> SCDA - Overview

NavData Cycle 2008-10 Expired: Thursday, 23 October 2008.

Scale: 1:3607646 (1 inch = 49.48 naut mi). Printed on 30 Oct 2008

7 6 9 9 6 ; 6 8

FliteStar 9.4.2.0

FAAM Sortie, Flight B412 - VOCALS 20°S Cross-section #3
Fri 31st October 2008

T/O - 0645 local (0945 UTC) – to change to a later time only if C-130 T/O is delayed.
Landing ~1145 local (1445 UTC)

Mission Scientists: Phil Brown, Keith Bower, Paul Barrett

Operating Area: SE Pacific Ocean, off west coast of northern Chile, along lat line 20S

Waypoints: **ALPHA:** 72°W 20°S
BRAVO: 79°30'W 20°S
DART Buoy 74°46.804'W 19°35.583'S

Sortie Objectives: To sample aerosol and Sc cloud as a function of distance from the coast to the pristine background (at times operating simultaneously with the Dornier 228 which will be remote sensing from FL150 - along same latitude) and to inter-compare in-situ cloud, aerosol and chemistry instruments/measurements with the C-130.

Weather: High pressure system off shore capping a marine boundary layer with widespread Sc cloud.

Detailed Flight schedule: PTO

Key Instrument Details:

SWS – as per instructions.

ARIES – as per instructions

CVI - During high level operate in aerosol mode with CVI hygrometer operating.

CVI – during in cloud runs operate in counterflow mode: **AMS** and **SP2** to sample from it

Wet Neph – operated during all of 500ft runs

Drosondes – 1 per degree of longitude on high level return between BRAVO and ALPHA

AMS, SMPS, SP2 – to operate from Rosemount inlets during aerosol and high level runs and profiles; to operate on CVI during in-cloud runs.

Filters – to be exposed on below cloud runs at discretion of mission Scientist(s). Blank to be undertaken on high level return. The sample tube should be blown through before first filter cartridges deployed

FAAM Sortie, Flight B412 - VOCALS 20°S Cross-section #3

Detailed Flight schedule:

1. Take off and profile ascent 1000 ft/min immediately to 6,000 ft amsl to check instrumentation
2. Continue towards ALPHA, beginning cycle below starting with immediate profile descent to 50ft.
3. Perform cycle consisting of a-i below
 - a. profile descent to 50ft amsl,
 - b. profile climb to 500ft amsl
 - c. carry out 10 min straight and level run (SLR) at 500ft amsl
 - d. * On first cycle only profile climb to 1500ft and carry out 3min SLR for CVI flow validation
 - e. climb to 500ft below cloudbase (CB),
 - f. carry out 10-min SLR at 500ft below CB,
 - g. climb to 500ft below cloud top (CT),
 - h. carry out 10-min SLR at 500ft below CT,
 - i. profile ascent to 1000ft above CT.
4. At point ALPHA turn onto westerly heading and continue profile cycle as described.
5. Repeat item 3 until arrival at point near to BRAVO. Continue on straight and level course and following communication with C-130 turn onto easterly heading to come into formation with C-130 to begin intercomparison legs [T=2h 25m]
6. Carry out 10min SLR at 500ft above CT, then descend to a point in-cloud at FL to be advised by the C-130.
7. Fly 10-minute straight and level in-cloud trailing the C-130 by 5 minutes.
8. Descend to 500 ft below cloud and fly 10 minute straight and level run.
9. Ascend to FL230 and turn to head west towards BRAVO until reaching a point along 20S from which to return to ALPHA (chosen so as to make full use of remaining fuel). After first contacting G1 and Do228 on guard freq 12345 to liase re: respective aircraft positions, begin to drop one sonde every 1 degree in longitude travelled towards ALPHA. NB no sondes to be dropped between point ALPHA and Arica on return.
10. Continue from point ALPHA to recover to Arica at FL230 as far as possible until approach into Arica and land [T=5h 00m]

BAe146 Mission Scientist debrief:

31 Oct 2008

Flight B412

20-deg-S cross-section

Philip R.A. Brown

Sortie Objectives:

To complete below- and in-cloud sampling along the 20S latitude, out to approximately 79.5W. At this point to join up with the C-130 and complete 3 10-min legs at approx 5 min trail, above, in and below cloud to obtain intercomparison data. Following completion of intercomparison, climb to FL230 for high level return transit along 20S, dropping sondes at 1-deg intervals.

Waypoints: Alpha 20.0S 72.0W
Bravo 20.0S 79.5W

Takeoff 0945 UT
Land 1450 UT

Cloud conditions:

Fig 1. GOES-10 Visible image at 1258UTC.

Cloud-free at Arica on takeoff. Thin/broken Sc during transit to Alpha, base 1800ft, tops ~2800ft. Cloud thickening along 20S, with some variability of cloudbase due to stronger convective circulations and boundary layer moisture structure. Temperature profiles appeared fairly well-mixed – structure mainly due to changes in humidity. Droplet concentrations along 20S 150-200 cm⁻³ at around 76W, 100-120 cm⁻³ at

78-79W. Little drizzle observed, but 30-40 l-1 drops with max diam 2-300 micron around 78W on outbound leg in-cloud. Return high-level leg came over increasingly broken cloud, with clear views to sea surface seen on downward-viewing Heimann radiometer.

Mission profile:

1. Climb out from Arica to 6000ft heading towards point Alpha.
2. Profile descent 1000ft/min to 50ft amsl. Cloud top 2800ft, base 1800ft.
3. One cycle of 10min legs at 500ft, 1300ft, 2500ft (low alt, below and in-cloud). Turn onto W heading at Alpha during middle leg. In-cloud leg has very broken thin cloud. Profile descent from 1000ft above cloud top to 50ft amsl.
4. 2nd cycle of legs, 500ft, 1800ft, 3300ft. Cloudbase ~2700ft but variable. Tdew variations seen along 1800ft leg and cloudbase occasionally only 1-200ft above. 3300ft leg is in the region of cumulus/lower cloudbase below the main Sc deck. Additional leg at 3700ft in the main cloud layer, LWC rising along run, droplet conc. 150-200 cm⁻³, mean diam 20 micron, maximum 30l-1 of drizzle drops max diam 300 micron. Profile descent from 1000ft above the cloud top level (=4500ft) to 50ft amsl.
5. 3rd cycle of legs at 500ft, 2300ft, 4100ft (in-cloud). Droplet concs 125-200 cm⁻³, mean diam. 20 micron. Cloud tops 5100ft at end. Altimeter setting 1020 hPa prior to this point.
6. 121657 UT commence turn back onto E heading to fall in behind the C-130 at 6000ft (on 1025hPa altimeter setting).
7. Trail ~5min behind C-130 to complete legs at 6000ft (above cloud), 4700ft (in cloud) and 500ft amsl (rad.alt). BAe146 run start and end times logged at the notified positions of C-130 runs. Altitude variations ~+/-20ft along runs. Cloud top 4900ft.
8. Rapid climb on W heading to FL230 and turn back E for high-level return leg. Moist layer at around 10000ft.
9. Dropsondes released at 1 deg longitude intervals from 78W to 72W (7 sondes). Nos. 2 and 6 have no wind data otherwise all OK.
10. From Point Alpha, profile descent 1000ft/min FL230 to 5000ft amsl followed by recovery to Arica. Moist layers seen at around 15000ft and 8000ft, with increased aerosol in each. Boundary layer v.hazy appearance during landing.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 412 Date 31/10/08 Name Peter Brown Page 1 of

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
0946					t/o ARI
					Cloud free at Arica but very hazy
0957		6000			transit.
/					cloudy a few miles offshore
100104		6000		19.00 S 70.54 W	start P1 thin with a few holes
/		2800			cloud top
/		1800			base wisps of Cu below.
1004					high aerosol layer.
100727		50			end P1
100834		500		19.3 S 71.3 W	start R1.1 cloud v. thin on the right.
101837		100			end R1.1
101935		1300			start 1.2 clear of cloud ahead e.w.
/					significantly drier to descent barber by ~ 3.5 deg.
102409				74 W 20 S	in town.
102936		1019			end 1.2
103044		2500			start 1.3 2550 ft.
					patchy cloud, thin & variable back.
103952		2600		73.00 W	run in & below cloud.
		11			end 1.3
		3500		73.60 W	tops - probably higher alt
/					3300 for next cloud leg.
104759		50			end P7
104848		500			start 2.1
					ccw higher cores but smaller

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 412 Date 31/10/08 Name Page 2 of

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
1053				73 54.0 W	Another cloud hole ahead and S.
105846		500		74 12.0 W	end 2.1
110016		1800	W	74 26. W	start 2.2. Continuing to become drier as go W wind 6ms ⁻¹ / 160 deg.
1105		"			Td rising - cloudbase only ~ 100-200 above.
1107					another Td peak.
111021		"		75.0 W	end 2.2, P10
111214		3300		75 60 W	start 2.3 2700 base but V. variable.
—					AMS, transition from acidic sulphate to organics. Poss sign of pollution plume.
—					This level seems to be in roots of the lower patches of cloudbase.
1118		"			now mostly clear of cloud. Just thro the cloud at end of run
112209		3300			end 2.3
112301		3700			start 2.4 in cloud?
1127		"			hwc rising ~ 0.2 gm ⁻³ CDP 150 20µm ↑ MFSSP 200 20µm.
1132					2DC → 30(-) 300µm max.
113354		"		76.360 W	end 2.4
		4500			tops... 400µm next in cloud.
		3500			base? 8ms ⁻¹ / 160
114231		50			end profile much more well mixed
114319		500		77 18.0 W	start 3.1 8 / 170

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 412 Date 31/10/08 Name Page 3 of

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
114930					still over patches of lower cloudbase ahead.
115115		500	W		Td rise here. wind 9/170
115323		"		77 54.0	end 3.1
115624		2300			just about Cu base. start 3.2
1158		"			below another lower base.
—		"			250 μ m drizzle
120531					end 3.2 base probably 3500
		¹⁰²⁰ 4100			start 3.2 C130 on 1025 ONH.
					CDP 125 20 μ m 2DC 30-40 μ m
—					M. 200 20 μ m 200-250 μ m
—		"			W +/- 2 $m s^{-1}$
—		¹⁰²⁵ 4250	on	1025	Two NTW track closely
					NW lower
121525					C130 on track.
121657					start turn.
121731		4100			end turn. P17
		¹⁰²⁵ 5100			tops.
		6000			end P17
122058				79 24 W 19 54 S	4.1 start - at C130 start pt.
					T 14.5 Td -22.13.
1228					Some Td variation. 78 41 W for start
1228					+/- 15ft height variance. 4700ft.
123048				78 42 W 20 S	end 4.1
123245		¹⁰²⁵ 4700		78 36 W	start 4.2 tops 4900
					sw - 0.5 $g m^{-3}$

MF 100 22-23 μ m (good with CAS)
CDP 120 23.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 242 Date 31/10/08 Name Page 4 of

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
	4.2	¹⁰²⁵ 4700			127/9ms ⁻¹ 123500 C130 end.
					JW & NTW good tracking.
1242					quite close to top.
124256		//		7800w	end 4.2 77 46. w f. 500ft. start
124637		500	radalt ↙		
124806		//			start 4.3. C130 start here.
					+/- 20ft vortn.
125230					AOSS showing 1° here
—					AOA/pitch good agreement.
					125300 C130 end.
—					145/8ms ⁻¹
—					cloud base looks fairly flat.
125812		500			end 4.3 & climb FL230 3500ft/min.
		¹⁰²¹ 4750			tops
—		10000			slight moist layer.
1310		¹⁰¹³ 23000			level.
131410	5	//	E		start @ 5.0
131506				78W	sonde 1 good data.
					286/23ms ⁻¹ .
1318					C130 at 75 30ish W
1320		//			GE -50C → check CR2 later.
132243		//			AOSS still 1deg.
132453				77W	sonde 2 no gps. sonde 1 splash.
1328					cloud break to NE (photos earlier).

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 412 Date 31/10/08 Name Page 5 of

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
133455	5	23000		76 W	sonde 3 good gps.
—				2 photos	prior to this - cloud break to N - change of cloud top character
—					line of cloud break seems to S
133745				to run consistently a few min N of track	
133900				75 W	photo for camera time check.
134505	"	"	1	75 W	sonde 4 good gps.
1348					small breaks in cloud seen in Heilmann.
—					larger lde ahead.
—					lower stratus good.
135515				74 W	sonde 5 probably in thin or clear area.
				↳	Heilmann just rising sonde will be on E side of clear area.
1356					Heilmann picking up surface and also the slight rise in cloud top temp as height reduces.
—					Ci on far NE horizon
1402		"			more broken areas around now, esp. ahead and S of track
140536		"	E	73 W	sonde 6 into thin/broken area - no gps at start.
	5				w = +/- 0.5 ms waves along track.
141620			"	72 W	sonde 7 into clear hole.
—					cloud at alpha pass.
					more broken than earlier.
142515		15000			layer here, pass across.
1430					photos ahead,
					- cloud edge
					- mokey BH
—					- high Andes with ocean Co to E
143715		8000	046		another layer, Andes

disappearing.
Sulphate & organic in the 15000 ft layer.

BH2 31/10/08 Instruments.

- CVI - change tip temp - Vbc impact on AMS
- CPC ok.
- Neph - OK both
- Filters - wet again. poss contaminants.
- SWS - lower errors ok.
- AMS - OK
- Core Chem - OK throughout
- Chl Phys - PCASP same symptoms as
UVU - χ/c conc., Chl high.
- FFSSP - hard disk glitches. but ok?
- ARIES/MARSS ok
- CCN - OK 0.1 & 0.2% continuous.
- VACE - ok.
- 2DS - 2 CAPS ok.
- SP2 - contaminated -
- Sondes - 7/2 no wind.
- Xchat - good throughout.
- Sat phone - ?
- Final profite ours to god.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...412... Date 3/10/08... Name P. BARRETT... Page 1 of 3

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
0940					74W 35S 500ft - C130 Position
0940					TAXI
0947	P1				T10
0949					invis at ~ 940m
0953					pt cloud below, broken cu thin
0958					END P1
					ceplayer at 5.2kft, clear at 4.6
	TRANSIT				- cloud thickening
10.01.00	P2	6.0kft			CLOUD TOP 2.8 kft
					Next at 700ft
				2.8	CLOUD BASE 1.8kft - diff.
10.06	100				Some cloud breaks above
				1.8	aerosol layer at 3.5kft
					MMW - 12-Satellite 1000', Trop-light SW
100833	1.1	500ft			
1016					broken cloud field above - 9/10 9/10
	P4				cu confusion + can't get 10min
	1.2				bright sun light [data not relayed]
10:24:34					POINT X after 30mins
					Broken cloud to 76°W, Salt IR-4
10344	P1.3	2.3			very thin Sc, broken, low LWC spikes
	P6.7				CLOUD TOP = 3.3 BASE =
					CCN - 700 below cloud, sea base
1046	2.1	500			

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B 412 Date 31/10/08 Name P. BARRETT Page 2 of 3

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					SP2 Flow 1.2 Lmin ⁻¹
	2.2				CCN falling with sun slips.
	2.3				
11:27.40	2.4	3.5		76°W	cloud thicker, LWC ~ 0.3 gm ⁻³ COP 150 p 200m increase PSSM 200 from 17 30k' @ 300m 2DZ - cloud top at 4.5 kft - more solid field of Sc now - cloud base ~ 3.2 kft Peak LWC at cloud base ~ 0.5 gm ⁻³
					Wing PLASP ~ 700 Gen PLASP ~ 60-70 CPC ~ 350 CPC _{gen} ~ 350
11:53.31	3.1	500			
11:57.53	3.2	2300			sub cloud (ish) CPC - sensitive to bank angle. Drizzle - 500m - 2 more CP
12:01.12					Drizzle CPC switching 30 seconds before end of run.
12:08.59	3.3	3.9 kft			cloud base 3.3 kft.
12:10					small drizzle. LWC = 16.2 LWC

LWC ~ 0.3

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B..... 412

Date 21/10/08

Name P. BARRETT

Page 3 of 3

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					FSSP - 200 ϕ 20
					CDP 125 ϕ 20
					2DC 30, 40 μ ϕ 200, 250
12:14:01					LWC increase at BRAVO 79.30'
					Need to set up an ashtray CT ~ 4.5, 4.7
12:20:59	4.1	5.6kt	92		Begin Intercomp above cloud CPL ~ 200, 220
12:32:39	4.2	4.7kt			cloud top just above 2DC ~ 50, 100 LWC ~ 0.3 $\rightarrow$ 0.5 μ m ³ near cloud top, bright FSSP 100 μ m 22, 23 μ m CDP 120 μ m 23 μ m
12:46:37					Cells - down draft, up draft circled
12:46:07					Start of run co-incident with C-130
					CPL LINES 300-350
					CPL intercomp - a spare one here that we could bring along
125813	EMD of 500 ft				
	AM) INTER COMPARISON				
	~ SONDE SECTION ~				

VOCALS BAe-146 Instrument status Report

Date of report(UTC): 2008/10/31 17:22

Author of report: Phil Brown

Submitted at(UTC): 2008/10/31 19:26

Remaining flight hours: 40

General Comments:

After mission on 31/10/2008

INSTRUMENTS / SYSTEMS STATUS

 = no report

Meteorology / Navigation

1.	GPS (Patch)	Comment:	
2.	GPS (Cruciform)	Comment:	
3.	Temperature/Pressure	Comment:	
4.	Water Vapor (Hygrometer)	Comment:	
5.	Turbulence Probe	Comment:	
6.	Altitude (RadarAlt)	Comment:	
7.	Doppler Radar	Comment:	
8.	Dropsonde (AVAPS)	Comment:	7 sondes launched - 2 had no wind data.

Radiation

9.	Broadband Radiometer (BBR)	Comment:	
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10.	Spectral Radiometer (ARIES)	Comment:
11.	In-flight Microwave Obs System (DEIMOS)	Comment:
12.	Microwave Radiometer Scanning System (MARSS)	Comment:
13.	Shortwave Spectrometer (SWS)	Comment:
14.	Spectral Irradiance (SHIM)	Comment: lower SHIMS working today
15.	Heimann Downward-facing Radiometer	Comment:

Chemistry

16.	Ozone (CAMP 2B)	Comment:
17.	NO _x	Comment:
18.	CO (AL5002)	Comment:
19.	SO ₂ (TECO 43C)	Comment:
20.	Sample Bottles (WAS)	Comment: not carried in VOCALS
21.	CH ₄ /CO ₂ (NIR-TDLAS)	Comment:
22.	PAN (GC)	Comment: not operated
23.	Volatile Aerosol Composition (VACC)	Comment:
24.	CH ₄ /N ₂ O (1C-TDLAS)	Comment:

Cloud Physics and Aerosol

25.	Liquid and Total water probe	Comment:	
26.	LWC (Johnson Williams)	Comment:	
27.	TWC	Comment:	
28.	FFSSP	Comment:	
29.	2D-C	Comment:	
30.	PCASP	Comment:	anomalous high counts observed. Needs investigation.
31.	Small Ice Detector (SID-2)	Comment:	not fitted
32.	Cloud and Precipitation Imager (CIP-15)	Comment:	needs alignment
33.	Cloud Droplet Probe (CDP)	Comment:	
34.	Condensation Nucleus Counter (CNC)	Comment:	
35.	Cloud Condensation Nuclei Spectrometer (CCNc)	Comment:	good throughout
36.	Fluorescence water vapour sensor (FWVS)	Comment:	
37.	Dry Nephelometer	Comment:	
38.	Wet Nephelometer	Comment:	
39.	Black Carbon (PSAP)	Comment:	
40.	Filters	Comment:	probable contamination from inlet
41.	Aerosol Mass Spectrometer (AMS)	Comment:	
42.	Counter-flow virtual Impactor (CVI)	Comment:	zero cals below cloud may be affected by drizzle

43.	2-D Imaging Probe (SPEC-2D-S-128H)	Comment:	
44.	CAPS	Comment:	
45.	Single Particle Soot Photometer (SP-2)	Comment:	optics contaminated mid-flight
46.	Fine-mode Aerosol Spectrometer (UHSAS)	Comment:	not fitted
47.	Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS)	Comment:	
48.	Ultrafine particle counter 1 (LP-WUCPC-1)	Comment:	
49.	Ultrafine particle counter 2 (LP-WUCPC-2)	Comment:	

Other

50.	SATCOM C	Comment:	
51.	SATCOM H	Comment:	Xchat working well. Phone not available.
52.	Up, Down, Front, Rear Digital Imagery	Comment:	

[prev](#) | [next](#)

 [Back to VOCALS Field Catalog](#) | [edit](#) | [delete](#)

comments : gstoss at ucar.edu

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 412

Date: 08:02:00	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
09:50:07	4000	0.08	0													FL020	
09:51:26	2000	0.08														FL030	
09:52:31	1000	0.07														FL040	
09:53:47	2200	0.08														FL050	
09:54:40	1300	0.08														End of Profile 1 @ FL060	
10:01:00	1800	0.08														Start Profile 2 from FL060	
10:02:16	1900	0.08														FL050	
10:03:06	3300	0.08														FL040	
10:03:57	2100	0.08	50													FL030	
10:04:54	2340	0.08														FL020	
10:05:47	3100	0.08														FL010	
10:07:25	3300	0.08														End of profile 2 @ 50'	
10:08:35																Start Run 1.1 @ 500'	
10:09:00	3100	0.08	50														
10:11:00	3210	0.08															
10:13:00	3220	0.08	51														
10:15:00	2930	0.08															
10:17:00	2900	0.08															
10:18:35																End of Run 1.1 & Start Profile 4 @ 500'	
10:19:23	2300	0.08														FL010	
10:19:37																End of Profile & Start Run 1.2 @ FL012	
10:20:00	2300	0.08															
10:22:00	2200	0.08															
10:24:00	2300	0.08															
10:26:00	2300	0.08															
10:28:00	2300	0.08															
10:29:35																End of Run 1.2 & Start Profile 5	
10:30:31	2300	0.08														FL020	
10:30:44																End of Profile 5 & Start Run 1.3 @ FL025	
10:31:00	2000	0.08	66			8	100	200	10			0.14	250	7	0.14	12	
10:33:00	1870	0.08	75														
10:35:00	1900	0.08				1		200	8				150	10	0.06		
10:37:00	2070	0.09				1	100	400	10				300	12	0.2	12	
10:39:00	1800	0.08	138														
10:40:39																End of Run 1.3 & Start Profile 6	
10:41:16	3900	0.14	190			3	100	100	10				250	15	0.3	12	
10:42:36	1200	0.14														End of Profile 6 & Start Profile 7 from FL040	
10:43:55	1400	0.08	214			1	100	400	10			0.4	300	15	0.25	12	
10:45:45	2400	0.07	227													FL010	
10:47:59	2300	0.07														End of Profile 7 & Start P8 from 50'	
10:48:48																End of Profile 8 & Start Run 2.1 @ 500'	
10:49:00	2300	0.07															
10:51:00	2400	0.07															

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.3V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.8 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 412

Date: 08:02:00	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
10:53:00	2250	0.07	228														
10:55:00	2000	0.07															
10:57:00	2000	0.07															
10:58:49																End of Run 2.1 & Start Profile 9	
10:59:47	1400	0.07														FL010	
11:00:14																End of P9 & Start Run 2.2 @ FL016	
11:01:00	1640	0.07															
11:03:00	1600	0.07															
11:05:00	1700	0.07															
11:07:00	1600	0.07															
11:09:00	1600	0.07															
11:10:16	1800	0.07	229													End of Run 2.2 & Start P10	
11:10:53	1500	0.07	230													FL020	
11:11:53																End of P9 & Start Run 2.3 @ 3300'	
11:12:00	2750	0.12	272			6	100	400	10			0.3	200	12	0.2	12	
11:14:00	1200	.08	286														
11:16:00	1300	0.07	290														
11:18:00	1300	0.07	291														
11:20:00	1300	0.07															
11:22:17																End of Run 2.3 & Start Profile 11	
11:22:49	1500	0.09														End of Profile 11 & Start Run 2.4 @ FL036	
11:24:00	1300	0.15	372			3	75	300	10			0.3	200	11	0.2	12	
11:26:00	3340	0.19	531			35	150	200	15			0.4	150	17	0.3	12	
11:28:00	3245	0.19	975			20	175	200	18			0.4	150	18	0.4	1	
11:30:00	4000	0.18	Fail														
11:32:00	4560	0.19	45			35	250	200	19			0.4	150	17	0.4	1	
11:34:57																End of Run 2.4 & Start Profile 12	
11:35:49	200	0.07														End of P12 & Start P13 from FL052	
11:37:14	5400	0.19	811			8	150	200	20			0.8	150	22	0.8	1	
11:38:17	650	0.08	870			1										FL040	
11:39:17	800	0.08														FL030	
11:40:20	700	0.08														FL020	
11:42:30	730	0.08														FL010	
11:43:20																End of Profile 13 & Start Profile 14 @ 50'	
11:44:00	760	0.08	873													End of Profile 14 & Start Run 3.1 @ 500'	
11:46:00	770	0.08															
11:48:00	800	0.08															
11:50:00	800	0.08															
11:52:00	700	0.08															
11:53:27																End of Run 3.1 & Start Profile 15	
11:54:15	550	0.07														FL010	
11:55:4	550	0.08														FL020	
11:55:35																End of Profile 15 & Start Run 3.2 @ 2300'	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.3V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.8 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 412

Date: 08:02:00	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
11:56:00	630	0.08	876														
11:58:00	710	0.08															
12:00:00	510	0.08															
12:02:00	600	0.08	877			1	200										
12:04:00	500	0.08					450										
12:05:34																End of Run & Start Profile 16	
12:07:45																End of Profile 16 & Start Run 3.3 @ FL039	
12:08:00	3000	0.19	1219			10	200	200	20			0.5	125	20	0.4	1	
12:10:00	3100	0.19	1450			12	200	200	20			0.5	125	20	0.4	1	
12:14:00	7000	0.19	1956			55	200	140	21			0.6	100	21	0.4	1	
12:16:00	2700	0.21	2715			20	300	100	21			0.4	80	20	0.2	1	
12:17:29																End of Run 3.3 & Start Profile 17	
12:18:08	4000	0.21	3176			30	100	100	22			0.7	100	25	0.6	12	
12:19:37																FL040	
12:20:57																End of Profile	
12:21:00	135	0.08														Start Run 4.1 @ FL057	
12:23:00	110	0.08															
12:25:00	100	0.08															
12:27:00	140	0.08															
12:29:00	110	0.08															
12:30:50																End of Run & Start Profile 18	
12:32:39																End of P18 & Start Run 4.2 @ 4700'	
12:33:00	7000	0.19	3425			60	225	100	22			0.9	100	23	0.6	1	
12:35:00	8000	0.18	4474			25	175	100	23			0.75	120	24	0.6	1	
12:37:00	5000	0.20	5000			100	175	100	22			0.8	100	25	0.8	1	
12:41:00	5000	0.20	5335			35	100	100	22			0.7	90	25	0.6	12	
12:43:02			FAIL													End of Run of Run & Start P19	
12:44:11	700	0.09	39			1	250									1	
12:45:07	800	0.09	40													FL030	
12:45:50	800	0.08														FL020	
12:46:30																FL010	
12:47:00	880	0.08														End of Profile 19 & Start Run 4.3 @ 500'	
12:49:00	880	0.08															
12:51:00	780	0.08															
12:53:00	800	0.08															
12:55:00	700	0.07															
12:57:00	700	0.08	95														
12:58:16																End of Run 4.3	
13:14:10																Start Run 5 @ FL230	
13:15:00	20	0.07	96														
13:17:00	5	0.08															
13:19:00	10	0.07															
13:21:00	5	0.07															

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.3V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.8 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 412

Date: 08:02:00	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 4 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
13:23:00	10	0.06	96														
13:25:00	15	0.08															
13:27:00	15	0.07															
13:29:00	7	0.07															
13:31:00	1	0.09															
13:33:00	19	0.08															
13:35:00	2	0.08															
13:37:00	10	0.08															
13:39:00	10	0.07															
13:41:00	10	0.07															
13:43:00	15	0.08															
13:45:00	15	0.07															
13:47:00	10	0.07															
13:49:00	10	0.07															
13:51:00	15	0.07															
13:53:00	10	0.07															
13:55:00	30	0.07															
13:57:00	30	0.07															
13:59:00	40	0.07	115														
14:01:00	40	0.07															
14:03:00	40	0.07															
14:05:00	50	0.07															
14:07:00	80	0.07															
14:09:00	90	0.07															
14:11:00	90	0.06															
14:13:00	90	0.06															
14:15:00	100	0.07															
14:17:00	90	0.07															
14:18:38	150	0.07														End of Run 5 & Start Profile 20 from FL230	
14:19:43	100	0.07														FL220	
14:20:48	130	0.07														FL210	
14:21:53	120	0.07														FL200	
14:23:15	110	0.07														FL190	
14:24:34	300	0.07														FL180	
14:25:55	1300	0.07														FL170	
14:27:15	1200	0.07														FL160	
14:28:08	1000	0.07														FL150	
14:29:30	400	0.07														FL140	
14:30:40	160	0.07														FL130	
14:31:58	70	0.07														FL120	
14:34:49	100	0.08														FL110	
14:34:37	80	0.08														FL100	
14:35:50	200	0.08														FL090	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.3V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.8 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

(5)

size	#	changed	Flight / Date	Discharged
10	1 } 2 }	30/10 (KMS)	B412 / (KMS) 31/10	Dropping Wet/Dirt
10	3 } 4 }	30/10 "	B412 / (KMS) 31/10	
10	7 } 8 }	30/10 "	B412 / (KMS) 31/10	Dropping Wet/Dirt
10	21 } 23 }	30/10 "	B412 / (KMS) 31/10	
10	33 } 40 }	30/10 "	B412 (KMS) 31/10	
10	10 } 64 }	3/10 "	B412 (KMS) 31/10	

Filter #	Loc'N	Tan	ToH	Run	Vol	Total
1, 2, 49	U	101945 110016	102948 111021	R1.2 R2.2	548 544	1125
3, 4, 140	U	115535	120535	R3.2	578	578
33, 40, 152	U	BLANK	BLANK	—	BLANK	—
7, 8, 117	L	100834 104848	101840 105851	R1.1 R2.1	598 802	1446
21 23 83	L	114320	115331	R3.1	607	667

CVI log

10/31/08 8:40:32 AM
10/31/08 8:42:27 AM
10/31/08 9:10:18 AM
10/31/08 9:13:37 AM look at pcasp preflight chn 1 - noise?
10/31/08 9:18:06 AM look at pcasp preflight chn 1 - noise?
10/31/08 9:18:51 AM look at oscil on lyman
10/31/08 9:57:49 AM hygro zero and back to sample
10/31/08 10:04:10 AM cloud
10/31/08 10:08:53 AM Strange oscilations in hygro, fairly regular
10/31/08 10:20:40 AM use 1300ft run for cvi zero
10/31/08 10:21:31 AM ams only to cvi, sp2 not on yet
10/31/08 10:23:28 AM sp2 to cvi
10/31/08 10:25:25 AM
10/31/08 10:26:08 AM
10/31/08 10:26:56 AM
10/31/08 10:28:04 AM
10/31/08 10:30:27 AM good zero with just AMS, but needed much higher control when SP2 switched. Does it draw more than 0,6??
10/31/08 10:30:58 AM in patchy cloud
10/31/08 10:40:26 AM just about no cloud on this run.
10/31/08 10:42:15 AM saw more cloud on profile up.
10/31/08 10:45:37 AM New cf is 4.8 (up from 3.8), are particle concentrtrions much reduced?
10/31/08 10:47:16 AM cf off aerosol mode
10/31/08 10:49:39 AM durin comparison, ams only in cloud, SP2 on rosemounts through out.
10/31/08 10:58:36 AM Manchester cloud rack drawing 1.2 not 0.6 lpm, will readjust dials and try cf control of 3.8 again.
10/31/08 11:10:13 AM cf on 30sec before end of run
10/31/08 11:11:09 AM cf on using 4.8 value to be sure, cpi dial at 0.6
10/31/08 11:11:48 AM in cloud
10/31/08 11:12:48 AM cloud very patchy
10/31/08 11:17:41 AM more out of cloud than in, so another in cloud run slightly higher planned.
10/31/08 11:23:14 AM 2nd cloud run, in cloud ish
10/31/08 11:31:26 AM All counts in CVI mode seem to low? but zero ok.
10/31/08 11:34:25 AM tip heater up to 45 from 20 for AMS
10/31/08 11:38:59 AM manchester back to rosemount
10/31/08 11:39:32 AM cf off aerosol mode
10/31/08 11:58:44 AM clipping some cloud bases
10/31/08 12:05:35 PM cf on.
10/31/08 12:06:45 PM cloud
10/31/08 12:14:28 PM tip heater back down to 20C for AMS check.
10/31/08 12:19:49 PM sp2 on rosemounts
10/31/08 12:20:04 PM sp2 on rosemounts
10/31/08 12:20:17 PM CVI only at cf:2.8
10/31/08 12:21:21 PM cf off aerosol mode
10/31/08 12:30:56 PM
10/31/08 12:31:06 PM cf on, ams only
10/31/08 12:32:03 PM in cloud
10/31/08 12:32:11 PM in cloud
10/31/08 12:47:18 PM cf off, aerosol mode
10/31/08 12:48:07 PM AMS not seeing anything for in cloud intercomparison run, CVI did see cloud but not large concentrations.
10/31/08 12:49:50 PM ams flow dial reset to 0.0
10/31/08 1:09:17 PM
10/31/08 2:58:23 PM hygro to zero

ARIES flight log

Flight: B412

page 1 of 2

Date: 31 OCT 2008 Operator(s): S. ROGERS

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: VOCALS 20°S

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
08 27 15	On the ground		CH	C	71	30	Cold Hot 1 min. script.
09 47	Takeoff						
10 08 34	500ft.	R1.1	NZ	O	71	30	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec. script
10 18 37	EOR ↑		-	C	71	31	- call in climb
10 19 35	1300 ?	R1.2	NZ	O	71	31	- continuation of NZ Long Run 3 min
							Clear above at start of run. Increasingly clouding over as run progresses
10 29 36	EOR ↑		-	C	71	31	
10 31 50		R1.3	CH	C	71	31	Cold Hot 1 min. script
10 48 48	500ft	R2.1	NZ	O	70	30	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec. script
10 58 51	EOR ↑		-	O	71	32	-
11 00 16	1800 ?	R2.2	NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec. script
11 10 21	EOR ↑		-	C	71	31	-
11 12 19			CH	C	71	31	Cold Hot 1 min. script
11 17 27	?		N	C	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 3 min For an in cloud run it's not very cloudy
11 22 22	↑ 3700		CH	C	71	31	Cold Hot 1 min script In cloud
11 26 43			CH	C	71	31	Cold Hot 1 min script
11 43 20	500ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec. script
11 53 31	EOR ↑		-	C	71	31	
11 55 35	2300ft	R3.2	NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec. Just below cloud.
12 05 35	EOR ↑		-	C	71	31	-
12 18 55			CH	C	71	31	Cold Hot 1 min
12 21 03		R4.1 240x1	N	C	71	30	Nadir Above cloud, following NCAR C-130
12 23 14			Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3 min Clear above
12 30	EOR ↓				71	30	↳ profile down during last Z view
12 34 22			N	C	71	31	Nadir Long Run 30 sec In cloud.
12 43	EOR ↓						
12 47 55	500ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 3 min
12 58 12	EOR ↑		-	C	71	31	
13 13 10	FL230		CH	C	71	30	Cold Hot 1 min script
13 14 30	"	240x1	Z	O	71	30	Zenith.
13 18 35	"		N	C	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min

B412_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

07:53:01.33 --- - - - -
07:53:01.33 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
07:53:01.33 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
07:53:01.33 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B412
07:53:01.35 --- - - - -
07:53:06.68 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
07:53:09.32 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
07:53:09.87 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
07:53:12.98 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:53:15.15 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:53:24.96 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:53:25.13 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:53:25.23 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:53:30.67 SWS - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:53:33.77 SWS - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 200ms.
07:53:33.77 SWS - - - 200 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 200ms.
07:53:36.22 USH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:53:38.63 USH - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 200ms.
07:53:38.63 USH - - - 200 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 200ms.
07:53:42.94 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:53:43.36 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:53:46.46 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:53:49.24 LSH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
07:53:49.24 LSH - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
07:53:53.01 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:53:53.02 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:53:53.02 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:54:25.70 LSH - 4000 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 4000ms.
07:54:34.77 LSH - 1000 - - - - Sample period changed from 4000ms to 1000ms.
07:54:49.81 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
07:54:58.36 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
07:55:05.23 SWS - - - - Idling
07:55:05.24 USH - - - - Idling
07:55:05.83 LSH - - - - Idling
07:55:41.86 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
07:55:43.51 SWS 170.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:02:30.00 --- - - - - *** 20 deg
08:03:48.21 --- - - - - *** 19 deg
08:05:45.17 SWS 174.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 100.000
08:05:46.28 SWS 100.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:06:31.78 --- - - - - *** 18 deg
08:09:17.13 --- - - - - *** 17 deg
08:13:18.68 --- - - - - *** 16 deg
08:15:59.31 --- - - - - *** 15 deg
08:18:47.50 --- - - - - *** 14 deg
08:20:19.70 --- - - - - *** 14 deg
08:20:55.13 --- - - - - *** 13 deg
08:30:45.83 --- - - - - *** 11 deg
08:31:36.67 --- - - - - *** 12 deg
08:34:54.27 --- - - - - *** 13 deg
08:35:58.76 --- - - - - *** 12 deg
08:38:51.07 --- - - - - *** 11 deg
08:42:33.61 --- - - - - *** 13 deg
09:11:00.80 --- - - - - *** 16 deg
09:16:11.21 --- - - - - ***
09:17:57.52 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:17:57.53 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:17:57.55 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:18:03.93 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:18:03.96 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:18:04.28 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:18:06.38 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:18:06.58 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:18:09.71 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:18:10.79 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:18:13.17 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.

```

09:18:13.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:18:13.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:18:15.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:18:16.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:18:19.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:21:57.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
09:25:10.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
09:32:18.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
09:33:00.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:33:02.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:33:03.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:33:06.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:33:07.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:33:13.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:35:13.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
09:37:04.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
09:50:19.74	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:50:32.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:50:32.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:50:32.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:50:34.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:50:34.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:50:38.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:09.23	SWS	100.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
09:56:10.37	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:56:16.30	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
09:56:18.03	SWS	173.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:56:21.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:21.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:22.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:24.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:24.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:28.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:01:09.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent to 50 ft
10:01:21.98	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:01:23.69	SWS	-5.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:01:26.90	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:01:32.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:01:32.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:01:33.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:01:34.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:01:34.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:01:39.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:04:27.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 2800 ft
10:05:35.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base diffuse but main base 1800 ft
10:07:27.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** 50 ft ascending
10:07:45.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:45.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:45.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:45.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:47.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:07:48.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:07:52.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:08:06.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:08:39.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 500 ft
10:08:46.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
10:13:08.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:08.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:08.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:19.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:19.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:19.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:21.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:22.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:22.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:22.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:25.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:25.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:25.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

10:13:26.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:26.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:26.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:28.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:29.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:32.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:41.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:13:41.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:13:41.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:14:57.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:14:57.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:14:57.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:14:59.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:09.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:09.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:09.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:11.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:15:12.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:12.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:12.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:14.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:15:14.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:15.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:15:17.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:17.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:17.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:20.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:15:20.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:24.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:15:25.76	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 40ms.
10:15:25.76	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 40ms.
10:15:28.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:29.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:15:31.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:32.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:15:33.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:34.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:15:34.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:35.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:15:43.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:43.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:48.69	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
10:15:48.71	USH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
10:15:50.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:51.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:52.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:53.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:55.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:16:02.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:42.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
10:19:35.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
10:20:53.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:53.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:53.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:08.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:08.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:08.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:08.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:09.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:11.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:11.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:12.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:12.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:13.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:13.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:14.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:14.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:14.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:15.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

10:21:15.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:15.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:15.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:16.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:21.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:31.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:31.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:31.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:55.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
10:23:02.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
10:26:26.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
10:26:56.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg??
10:27:13.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** 18 deg
10:27:45.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
10:27:55.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:27:55.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:27:55.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:28:07.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:28:07.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:28:07.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:28:08.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:28:08.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:28:09.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:28:09.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:28:10.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:28:11.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:28:12.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:28:12.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:28:13.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:28:13.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:28:13.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:28:13.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:28:14.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:28:14.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:28:14.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:28:15.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:28:29.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:28:29.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:28:29.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:13.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
10:35:38.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
10:39:02.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
10:39:19.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:39:26.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:39:29.85	LSH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
10:39:34.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:39:40.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:51.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:58.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:01.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:07.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:41:07.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:41:08.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:16.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:16.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:17.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:17.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:41:18.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:41:22.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:22.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:23.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:41:23.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:41:23.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:25.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:25.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:25.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:25.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:41:26.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:41:31.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

10:41:34.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:34.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:55.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
10:42:41.55	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:46:16.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
10:49:22.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:49:22.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:49:22.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:49:29.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:29.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:29.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:30.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:49:30.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:49:36.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:49:37.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:37.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:37.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:38.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:49:38.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:49:44.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:49:52.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:52.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:52.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:51:34.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
10:52:18.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
10:55:29.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
11:02:09.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:02:09.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:02:09.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:02:21.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:02:21.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:02:21.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:02:22.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:02:23.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:02:27.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:02:27.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:02:27.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:02:28.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:02:28.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:02:29.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:02:29.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:02:29.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:02:30.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:02:30.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:02:36.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:02:36.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:02:36.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:02:36.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:02:37.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:02:37.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:02:43.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:02:45.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:02:45.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:02:45.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:03:29.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
11:10:21.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:22.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:22.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:22.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:28.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:28.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:28.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:29.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:30.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:31.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:31.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:32.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:32.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:35.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

11:10:36.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:36.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:36.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:36.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:37.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:43.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:44.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:44.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:44.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:45.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:45.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:51.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:53.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:53.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:53.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:12:07.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
11:12:16.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud run
11:12:47.84	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:12:49.58	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:14:23.92	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:14:25.63	SWS	-5.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:15:01.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:01.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:01.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:12.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:12.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:12.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:13.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:13.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:17.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:17.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:18.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:18.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:18.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:21.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:21.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:21.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:21.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:22.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:27.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:28.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:28.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:28.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:28.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:29.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:34.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:36.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:36.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:36.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:18:15.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
11:25:12.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
11:27:24.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:24.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:24.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:27.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:27.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:27.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:46.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:46.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:46.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:09.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:09.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:09.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:10.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:10.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:12.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:12.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:13.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:13.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

11:28:15.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:15.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:16.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:16.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:16.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:25.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:28:25.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:28:25.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:28:51.18	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:28:52.92	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:30:42.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
11:31:40.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
11:32:30.35	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:32:32.09	SWS	-5.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:33:26.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
11:35:02.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 4500 ft
11:36:04.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:11.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:53.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
11:43:49.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 500 ft
11:48:53.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
11:49:41.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:49:41.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:49:41.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:49:48.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:49:48.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:49:48.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:49:49.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:49:49.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:49:55.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:49:55.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:49:55.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:49:55.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:49:56.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:49:56.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:02.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:02.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:02.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:02.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:03.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:04.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:09.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:10.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:10.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:10.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:19.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
11:55:40.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:55:41.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:55:41.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:55:48.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:55:48.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:55:48.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:55:49.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:55:49.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:55:55.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:55:55.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:55:55.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:55:55.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:55:56.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:55:56.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:56:02.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:56:06.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:56:06.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:56:06.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:56:41.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 2300 ft below cloud but skimming cloud base
11:57:44.35	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:57:46.09	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:58:52.48	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000

11:58:54.25	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:04:40.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
12:08:10.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud run
12:09:00.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:00.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:00.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:08.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:08.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:08.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:09.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:09.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:14.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:15.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:15.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:15.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:16.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:16.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:21.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:22.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:09:22.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:09:22.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:09:36.21	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:09:37.98	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:09:53.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
12:11:44.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
12:12:03.37	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:12:05.14	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:16:31.02	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:16:32.78	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:18:11.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
12:20:06.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** C130 intercomparison
12:20:19.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:20:25.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:30.00	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 200ms.
12:20:30.01	LSH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 200ms.
12:20:32.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:20:35.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:51.62	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
12:20:51.63	LSH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
12:20:53.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:20:54.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:56.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:20:58.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:21:05.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 4.1
12:21:17.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** above cloud
12:21:20.99	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:21:22.76	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:21:54.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:21:54.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:21:54.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:00.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:00.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:00.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:01.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:02.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:02.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:03.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:03.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:03.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:04.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:04.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:04.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:10.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:22:10.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:22:10.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:23:04.42	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:23:06.20	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:23:46.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
12:23:49.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

12:23:50.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:23:53.11	USH	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 40ms.
12:23:53.13	USH	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 40ms.
12:23:55.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:56.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:23:57.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:58.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:44.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
12:26:57.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
12:32:40.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 4.2 in cloud intercomparison run
12:33:16.32	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:33:18.08	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:33:33.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:33.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:33.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:38.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:38.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:38.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:39.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:40.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:40.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:41.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:41.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:41.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:42.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:43.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:43.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:48.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:33:48.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:33:48.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:34:01.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
12:35:32.81	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:35:34.58	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:38:37.44	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:38:39.21	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:40:55.65	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:40:57.43	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:42:36.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
12:42:59.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run profile descent
12:46:34.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** below cloud intercomparison run 500 ft amsl
12:46:38.53	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:46:40.25	SWS	-5.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:47:05.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:05.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:05.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:09.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:09.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:09.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:10.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:11.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:11.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:13.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:13.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:13.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:14.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:15.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:15.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:16.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:16.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:16.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:17.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:17.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:17.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:18.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:24.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:47:24.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:47:24.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:53:05.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg

```

12:58:13.62 --- - - - - *** end of run
12:58:58.26 --- - - - - *** climb to fl 230 end of c130
intercomparison
13:02:34.34 --- - - - - *** 13 deg
13:08:51.04 LSH - - - - Idling
13:08:51.10 USH - - - - Idling
13:08:51.16 SWS - - - - Idling
13:09:07.04 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:09:07.05 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:09:07.06 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:09:07.91 SWS - - - - Idling
13:09:08.34 USH - - - - Idling
13:09:08.75 LSH - - - - Idling
13:09:09.90 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:09:09.91 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:09:09.93 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:09:10.77 SWS - - - - Idling
13:09:11.20 USH - - - - Idling
13:09:11.74 LSH - - - - Idling
13:09:11.75 LSH - - - - Idling
13:09:12.51 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:09:12.52 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:09:12.54 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:09:13.58 USH - - - - Idling
13:09:13.82 SWS - - - - Idling
13:09:14.02 LSH - - - - Idling
13:09:18.62 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:09:18.62 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:09:18.63 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:09:34.06 --- - - - - *** 12 deg
13:11:41.96 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
13:11:42.44 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:11:43.74 SWS 174.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
13:13:26.07 SWS 174.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
13:13:27.87 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
13:13:36.84 LSH - - - - Idling
13:13:36.86 SWS - - - - Idling
13:13:36.89 USH - - - - Idling
13:13:42.14 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:13:42.15 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:13:42.16 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:13:43.04 USH - - - - Idling
13:13:43.43 SWS - - - - Idling
13:13:43.84 LSH - - - - Idling
13:13:44.80 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:13:44.80 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:13:44.81 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:13:45.65 SWS - - - - Idling
13:13:46.12 USH - - - - Idling
13:13:46.48 LSH - - - - Idling
13:13:47.13 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:13:47.13 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:13:47.15 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:13:48.03 SWS - - - - Idling
13:13:48.46 USH - - - - Idling
13:13:48.88 LSH - - - - Idling
13:13:50.12 SWS - - 30 - VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
13:13:50.13 SWS - - - 30 NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
13:13:52.68 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:13:52.68 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:13:52.71 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:13:53.91 SWS - - - - Idling
13:13:54.04 USH - - - - Idling
13:13:54.61 LSH - - - - Idling
13:13:56.27 USH - - 25 - VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 25ms.
13:13:56.28 USH - - - 25 NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 25ms.
13:13:58.69 USH - - 30 - VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 30ms.
13:13:58.69 USH - - - 30 NIR int.time changed from 25ms to 30ms.
13:14:00.05 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.

```

13:14:00.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:14:00.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:14:01.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:14:01.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:14:02.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:14:02.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:14:02.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:14:02.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:14:02.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:14:03.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:14:03.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:14:08.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:14:08.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:14:08.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:14:11.25	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:14:13.05	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:16:42.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
13:17:52.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
13:24:15.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
13:26:23.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:26:23.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:26:23.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:26:33.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:26:34.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:26:34.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:26:34.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:26:35.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:26:35.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:26:36.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:26:36.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:26:36.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:26:37.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:26:37.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:26:38.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:26:39.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:26:39.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:26:39.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:26:40.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:26:40.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:26:41.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:26:48.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:26:48.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:26:48.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:30:18.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
13:30:34.77	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:30:36.63	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:30:53.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:53.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:53.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:59.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:30:59.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:30:59.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:00.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:01.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:01.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:03.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:03.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:03.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:04.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:04.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:04.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:05.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:05.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:05.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:06.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:07.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:07.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:15.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:31:15.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

13:31:15.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:32:12.29	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:32:14.08	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:39:02.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:39:02.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:39:02.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:39:12.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:39:12.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:39:12.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:39:12.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:39:13.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:39:13.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:39:13.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:39:14.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:39:16.13	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:39:20.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:39:20.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:39:20.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:39:21.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:39:21.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:39:21.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:39:23.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:39:23.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:39:23.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:39:24.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:39:25.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:39:25.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:39:27.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:39:27.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:39:27.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:39:27.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:39:28.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:39:28.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:39:37.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:39:37.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:39:37.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:41:48.95	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:41:50.72	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:43:08.82	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:43:12.74	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:43:14.57	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:43:24.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
13:52:19.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
13:52:45.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** breaks in cloud below
13:53:53.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
13:56:55.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:55.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:55.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:01.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:01.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:01.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:02.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:57:02.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:57:02.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:02.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:03.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:04.28	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:57:08.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:08.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:08.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:09.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:09.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:10.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:11.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:11.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:11.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:11.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:12.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:12.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

13:57:13.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:13.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:13.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:14.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:14.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:15.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:20.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:57:20.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:57:20.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:58:31.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
14:01:55.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:55.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:57.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:58.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:00.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:01.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:45.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:45.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:45.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:50.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:50.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:50.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:51.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:51.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:51.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:53.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:53.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:53.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:53.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:54.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:54.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:59.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:59.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:59.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:06:41.79	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 173.500
14:06:44.27	SWS	173.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:06:45.29	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.500
14:11:54.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
14:12:13.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:13.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:13.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:15.59	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:12:21.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:21.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:21.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:22.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:22.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:23.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:24.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:24.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:24.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:24.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:25.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:25.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:26.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:26.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:26.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:27.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:28.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:28.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:33.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:12:33.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:12:33.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:13:48.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
14:18:44.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
14:18:48.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
14:18:56.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 20
14:19:03.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:03.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

14:19:03.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:04.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:05.57	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:19:11.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:11.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:11.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:12.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:12.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:13.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:14.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:14.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:14.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:15.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:15.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:16.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:16.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:16.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:16.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:17.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:17.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:18.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:23.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:19:23.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:19:23.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:16.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
14:27:22.22	SWS	174.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
14:27:24.02	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:29:05.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
14:29:56.12	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.500
14:29:57.91	SWS	174.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:39:10.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** layer of aerosol just above cloud top
14:40:25.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
14:40:43.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud sheet very broken
14:40:57.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** only patchy cloud
14:42:21.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** going through cloud layer now (or height of cloud layer if miss cloud)
14:54:14.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** 1
14:54:14.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:54:14.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:54:14.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:54:18.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
14:54:21.91	SWS	174.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
14:54:23.70	SWS	-5.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:54:28.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:54:28.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:54:28.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:54:44.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:54:44.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:54:44.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:54:44.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:54:45.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:54:46.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:54:46.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:07.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:07.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:07.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:13.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:13.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:13.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:13.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:14.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:15.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:15.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:15.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:15.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:16.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:16.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:16.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:17.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

14:55:17.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:17.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:18.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:19.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:19.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:20.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:20.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:20.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:21.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:21.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:22.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:28.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:28.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:28.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

BA12

'off window'

Flight:

B412

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B412

Date: 31/oct/08

Instruments

CVI -	ok
Neph	ok
PSAP	ok
WetNeph	ok
Filters	pipework needs cleaning
SWS -	ok, using manual shutter control
SHIMS -	upper ok lower ok
AMS	ok
Core Chem -	CO good, using manual cals SO2 ok Nox ok O3 ok
Cloud physics -	PCASP concentrations high channel 1 noise FSSP ok, hard disc annoyance
ARIES -	ok
MARSS -	ok
CCN -	run unmanned ok
VACC -	good operation
2DS -	ok
CAPS -	ok
SMPS -	ok
Buck -	not operated
SP2	contaminated
Sondes	7 launched 5 ok, 2 didn't get gps lock

Aircraft

ISDN Emails

1 email

MPDS

Run for approx 4 hours (Xchat)

Satcom-H Calls

Nil - no dial tone

Issues

Upper BBRs need cleaning before every flight
MPDS & ISDN could not run simultaneously
Satcom handset not working ?

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 31/10/08

Flight No: B412

Pre-Flighter: KT (under watchful eye of MS)

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	X	Hangar	Collect spanners for core chem	
Aircraft Cabin: Power-up				
2	DA	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	✓	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	DA	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
5	DA	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
6	✓	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	✓	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	✓	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	✓	HORACE	Recording data	
10	✓	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	✓	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	✓	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	✓	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	ish	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	too dark
15	✓	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	X	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	
17	✓	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	✓	Helmann	Calibration Checked	
19	✓	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	✓	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	✓	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	✓	Satcom C	Checked	
23	X	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	✓	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
25	X	CNC	Butanol filled	
26	DT	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	DT	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
28	X	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
External Checks				
29	✓	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	✓	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	✓	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	✓	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	✓	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	✓	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	✓	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	clear has bits in
36	✓	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	✓	Helmann	Lens checked OK	residual dots
38	✓	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	✓	All other covers	Removed	
40		Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
41		Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42		Tools	Avalon informed	
Avalon Checks				Signed
44	X	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
45	X	ICEX applied		
46	X	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -	a)Nil b)1-2 drops c)1/4 full or more	
47	X	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B412:

Log	Reason
Instrument Status	may not be correct – Flight Manager asked to check
Cloud Physics Processing	No cloud physics processing logs are expected for VOCALS flights
MARSS	No log, set running by Jeff then monitored in flight by Stuart Rogers
VACC	Operator does not create a log sheet
2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	24 Jul 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_094203_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_095114_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_105114_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_115114_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_125114_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_135114_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_094148_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_104148_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_114148_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_124148_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_134148_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_144148_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_092255_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_094141_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_104141_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_114141_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_124141_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_134141_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_144141_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_094157_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_104157_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_114157_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_124157_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_134157_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_144157_1hz.avi

Problems with file conversion:
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081031_r0_b412_135114_1hz.raw
 did not convert properly.

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.